

The Role of Work Ethic in Mediating the Relationship Between Resilience and Employee Performance in the Operations Department of PT. Wanho Industries Indonesia in Batang Regency

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The authors declare that no funding was received for this work.

Received: 21-November-2025

Accepted: 31-December-2025

Published: 03-January-2026

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This article is published in the **MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (MSIJMR)** ISSN 3049-0669 (Online)

The journal is managed and published by MSI Publishers.

Volume: 3, Issue: 1 (January-2026)

ABSTRACT: In the era of globalization and increasingly fierce business competition, the manufacturing industry faces various challenges that require high levels of adaptability and resilience from its employees. Rapid technological change, supply chain disruptions, and skilled labor shortages are key challenges facing manufacturing companies in the modern era. This study aims to examine the direct and indirect effects of resilience on employee performance and work ethic on employee performance. The population of this study was 466 employees of the Operations Department of PT. Wanho Industries Indonesia. The sampling method was proportional random sampling, with a sample size of 82 people. The analytical technique used was path analysis. The results showed that resilience had a positive but insignificant effect on employee performance. Work ethic had a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Resilience was shown to have a positive and significant effect on work ethic. Intervening tests showed that resilience indirectly influences performance through work ethic, thus indicating that work ethic fully mediates the relationship. This finding reinforces the importance of work ethic as a bridging mechanism between resilience's influence on performance.

Keywords: *resilience, work ethic, employee performance, mediation.*

Introduction

In the era of globalization and increasing business competition, the manufacturing sector faces various challenges that require high adaptability and resilience from its employees. Rapid technological change, supply chain disruptions, and skilled labor shortages are key challenges facing manufacturing companies in this modern era. Therefore, companies need to develop the potential of their human resources (Deloitte, 2023). Human resources play a crucial role in an organization or business and must be managed effectively to improve organizational performance and achieve business goals. (Putri & Mujanah, 2023)

Employee performance is the main foundation in determining organizational success because high-performing employees are able to drive the achievement of strategic goals and maintain organizational competitiveness amidst increasingly fierce global competition (Mangkunegara, 2011). Improving employee performance in practice does not always run smoothly due to work challenges, environmental pressures, and dynamic organizational changes (Bakker et al., 2023). Work pressure can reduce performance, as found in the healthcare sector where work stress reduces focus and task effectiveness (Deng et al., 2019) Even negative emotions such as fear have been shown to suppress various dimensions of performance, from task performance, contextual, to creative (Wang et al., 2022). This shows that employee performance is not only influenced by technical and structural factors, but also by individual psychological characteristics such as resilience.

Resilience is an individual's ability to bounce back from adversity, adapt to change, and maintain optimal performance in the face of stress or adversity (Zhai et al., 2023). The concept of resilience in an organizational context has received increasing attention, particularly following various global crises that have demonstrated the importance of adaptability and resilience in maintaining organizational performance. Recent research has shown that organizational resilience has a significant impact on employee performance, particularly during economic crises (Pühringer & Wolfmayr, 2024)

Recent meta-analytic research shows that workplace resilience has a significant positive relationship with various positive outcomes such as engagement, job satisfaction, and performance (PMC, 2024). These findings indicate that employees with high levels of resilience tend to perform better, especially when facing challenges and high work pressure. The direct relationship between resilience and performance still shows mixed results, so intervening variables are needed to explain the mechanisms of this influence (Al Halbusi et al., 2022). One factor suspected to play a significant role as an intervening variable is work ethic.

Work ethic is an individual's attitude and orientation toward work, encompassing values such as dedication, responsibility, integrity, and commitment to quality work (Sipahelut et al., 2021). Research shows that work ethic has a significant positive influence on employee performance in various organizational contexts (Atlantis Press, 2024). A strong work ethic can be a key driver that drives employees to achieve optimal performance, even in challenging situations. In the context of manufacturing companies, where consistency, quality, and production efficiency are key to success, work ethic is a crucial factor.

The link between resilience and work ethic can be understood through a positive psychology perspective. Employees with high resilience tend to have a positive outlook on challenges, the ability to maintain motivation in difficult situations, and perseverance in the face of obstacles. These characteristics align closely with the values inherent in a strong work ethic. Therefore, resilience can strengthen employees' work ethic, which in turn positively impacts their performance.

Research results indicate that work ethic can act as an intervening variable in the relationship between various individual factors and employee performance. Studies conducted by researchers indicate that work ethic can mediate the influence of the work environment on employee performance (Society, 2023). However, research specifically examining the role of work ethic as an intervening variable in the relationship between resilience and employee performance, particularly in the context of manufacturing companies, is still very limited.

The manufacturing sector has unique characteristics that set it apart from other

sectors. Challenging work environments, pressure to meet production targets, the need to maintain product quality, and the demands of adapting to new technologies create conditions that require a high level of resilience and work ethic from employees. Research shows that manufacturing companies that demonstrate high resilience tend to survive and even thrive in the face of economic uncertainty (Newswire, 2001)

In developing countries, the manufacturing sector continues to grow, further emphasizing the urgency of this research. Manufacturing companies face dual challenges: the pressures of global competition and the need to develop qualified human resources. Under these conditions, a thorough understanding of the factors that can improve employee performance is crucial for the advancement of the national manufacturing industry.

The research gap shows that although the relationship between resilience and performance has been extensively studied, the role of work ethic as a mechanism explaining how resilience influences performance remains underexplored. Most previous studies have focused on the direct relationship between resilience and performance, without considering the psychological and behavioral processes that connect the two.

Research specifically examining this phenomenon in the context of manufacturing companies is still very limited. However, the manufacturing industry's unique characteristics, such as a dynamic work environment, high operational pressure, and the need for continuous innovation, can provide a unique context for understanding the relationship between resilience, work ethic, and employee performance.

This research aims to fill this theoretical and empirical gap by comprehensively examining the influence of resilience on employee performance through the mediation of work ethic in the context of manufacturing companies. The findings of this study are expected to provide theoretical contributions to the development of human resource management science, particularly in understanding the psychological mechanisms underlying employee performance.

From a practical perspective, this research is expected to provide insights for

manufacturing company management in developing more effective human resource management strategies. Understanding how resilience influences performance through work ethic can assist organizations in designing employee development programs, performance management systems, and organizational policies that can improve productivity and competitiveness.

The subject of this research is PT. Wanho Industries Indonesia, Batang Regency, a manufacturing company that produces die-cast car miniatures. In its production, the company prioritizes resilience in facing industry challenges, encouraging individuals to remain resilient and focused on their tasks. The work ethic then transforms this resilience into disciplined, diligent, and productive work behaviors, thereby improving performance.

Based on the results of the 2024 employee performance evaluation, there is a difference between the realization and the company's expected targets, which are presented in table one as follows:

Table 1: Employee Performance Evaluation of PT. Wanho Industries Indonesia, Batang Regency, 2024

No	Description	Target	Realisasi	Achievements
1	Annual Production Target	125000 Pcs	91642 Pcs	73%
2	Production Cost Efficiency	10 %	10,20 %	102%
3	Employee Attendance	100%	83%	83%
4	New Product Innovation (per Year)	9 Pcs	5 Pcs	56%
5	Sales (per Year)	10 %	13%	150%
6	Employee Turn Over Rate (per Year)	9%	12%	133%

Source: PT. Wanho Industries Indonesia Personnel, Batang Regency 2025

Data from PT. Wanho Industries Indonesia shows varying levels of achievement in several performance aspects. The annual production target of 125,000 units was only 73% achieved, with 91,642 units produced. This was due to changes in market demand and the termination of partnerships with distributors, resulting in the target

not being met. On the other hand, production cost efficiency exceeded the target with an achievement of 102%, reaching 10.20%, which indicates good cost management. The employee attendance rate only reached 83% of the target of 100%, this was due to frequent health problems experienced by employees and a lack of employee motivation and engagement. New product innovation only reached 56% of the target, but sales increased beyond the target, reaching 150% of the set target. This indicates improving sales growth. Employee turnover reached 133% of the target, driven by dissatisfaction with the work environment, limited career development opportunities, and excessive workloads, which led to stress and the decision to seek employment elsewhere.

Based on the description above, the problem can be formulated as follows: how does resilience affect work ethic? How does work ethic affect employee performance? How does resilience affect employee performance, both directly and through work ethic? The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of resilience on work ethic, to determine the effect of work ethic on employee performance, to determine resilience on employee performance, both directly and through work ethic.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Performance

(Faried et al., 2024) state that performance is a manifestation of an individual's behavior within an organization with an achievement orientation. Performance is about what is done, how it is done, and the results achieved from that work. (Pangestu, 2024). (Muspawi, 2021) explains that performance is the work results achieved by an individual or group in carrying out tasks according to their responsibilities and authority within an organization based on performance standards or measures and timeframes tailored to the type of work and in accordance with established norms and ethics.

Every employee has performance standards that motivate them to carry out their work. This is intended to enable employees to exceed established standards. Performance standards are defined as the standards for employee performance that have been established to achieve goals. According to Prasetyo & Isnowati (2022),

performance is the work results achieved by an individual based on job requirements. A job has specific requirements to achieve these goals, also known as job standards. Each company typically has different job standards, typically based on the company's stated goals.

Based on the opinions of the experts above, employee performance can be defined as an employee's ability to carry out his duties according to his responsibilities and authority based on standards or measurements and time adjusted to the type of work which includes quality, quantity, timeliness, effectiveness, independence and commitment, with indicators of quality, quantity, timeliness, effectiveness, efficiency, independence, commitment

Resilience

Resilience is an individual's ability to bounce back, adapt, and maintain optimal functioning in the face of stress, challenges, and failure at work (Luthans et al., 2006). In an organizational context, resilience is viewed as psychological capital that enables employees to remain productive even in stressful situations. Resilient individuals are able to manage stress, maintain motivation, and demonstrate consistent work behavior. The Conservation of Resources (COR) theory explains that resilience functions as a psychological resource that helps individuals maintain positive energy and prevent burnout due to work demands (Mazzetti et al., 2024).

Similarly, resilience is an individual's ability to cope and adapt to challenging events or challenges in life (Pratiwi & Yuliandri, 2022). Resilience is the process of adapting effectively in the face of adversity, trauma, threats, or other sources of stress. Being resilient does not mean a person is immune to adversity. (Pragholapati, 2020) explains that resilience is a person's ability to persevere and not give up easily in difficult situations, while striving to adapt to these circumstances, then recovering and becoming a better person.

Based on the opinions above, the definition of resilience is the ability of employees to survive, adapt, and bounce back from work pressure or failure, with indicators of adaptability, ability to bounce back, ability to overcome anxiety, ability to overcome stress.

Work Ethic

Wibowo & Harri (2023) state that work ethic is a set of fundamental attitudes or views held by employees, regarding work as a positive factor in improving the quality of life, thus influencing their work behavior within the organization. Tangkudung & Taroreh (2021) state that work ethic has different meanings, but in principle, it shares the same goal: focusing on basic human attitudes.

Mila et al. (2023) explain that work ethic is a work spirit that is characteristic of a person or group of people who work, which is based on work ethics and perspectives that are believed in and manifested through concrete behavioral determination in the world of work. Meanwhile, according to Purnomo & Nugroho (2023), work ethic is a work spirit possessed by employees to be able to work better in order to obtain added value in a job. Work ethic is not only reflected in enthusiasm and motivation, but also in concrete employee actions such as compliance with rules, commitment to completing tasks on time, and integrity in work. Based on several opinions above, the definition of work ethic is the work spirit possessed by employees to be able to work better in order to obtain added value in a job that is demonstrated by hard work, discipline, honesty and diligence, with indicators of hard work, discipline, honesty, diligence

Employee Resilience and Performance

Resilience is an individual's ability to remain productive despite facing pressure, obstacles, and work failures. Resilient employees are able to survive and adapt more quickly, manage stress, and maintain focus on work goals, thus maintaining optimal performance. They can adapt to change, manage negative emotions, and find solutions to emerging problems. This can have a positive impact on employee performance. Resilient employees will demonstrate consistent, high-quality work results because they are able to remain focused and productive even in challenging situations. Furthermore, they also have a strong sense of responsibility in completing their tasks on time.

Resilience also enables employees to be more collaborative and work effectively as part of a team to achieve organizational goals. When employees can cope well with

challenges and change, they tend to be more motivated, satisfied, and committed to their work. Thus, resilience can be a crucial factor influencing employee performance within an organization. A deep understanding of the relationship between resilience and employee performance can help companies design more effective human resource management strategies, thereby enhancing their competitiveness in a dynamic business environment.

Research by Ocktafian (2021) Faried et al (2024), and Putri & Mujanah (2023) indicates that resilience has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This means that the better an employee's resilience, the higher their performance will be. Therefore, this research hypothesis is:

H1: Resilience has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Work Ethic and Performance

Work ethic is a set of values, attitudes, and beliefs that motivate individuals to work with discipline, honesty, responsibility, and dedication. Employees with a strong work ethic tend to display consistent, diligent, and goal-oriented work behavior, thus directly contributing to improved performance. According to Work Ethic Theory, an individual's internalized work values will guide productive behavior and influence work outcomes (Weber & Kalberg, 2013); and are reinforced (Zawawi et al., 2025).

Empirical evidence shows that work ethic has a positive and significant impact on employee performance, both in the manufacturing and service sectors, because work values such as discipline and responsibility drive the quality and quantity of work output (Ilhami et al., 2024). Recent research in the oil and gas industry in Indonesia also found that work ethic plays a significant role in improving employee performance, particularly when integrated with organizational support and a conducive work environment ((Suprpto et al., 2025). Therefore, the stronger an employee's work ethic, the higher their performance within the organization. Based on this thinking, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H2: Work ethic has a positive and significant impact on employee performance.

Resilience and Work Ethic

Resilience is an individual's ability to overcome stress, setbacks, and difficulties in the workplace without losing enthusiasm. Resilient employees tend to view stress and challenges as opportunities for growth, rather than threats. They continue to work enthusiastically and adapt easily despite changes in company policy. This aligns with the Conservation of Resources Theory (COR), which states that individuals with strong psychological resources, such as optimism, self-efficacy, and hope, are better able to maintain the energy to act in a disciplined, diligent, and responsible manner (Mazzetti et al., 2024). This behavior reflects work ethic, a set of values and attitudes that encourage an individual to work honestly, responsibly, and with dedication ((Sinamo,, 2011).

Empirical evidence shows that resilience has a positive effect on work ethic, as resilient employees are better able to maintain a consistent and valued work attitude despite facing pressure ((Al Halbusi et al., 2022). Other research also confirms that resilience contributes to a positive work attitude, which in turn strengthens employee work ethic Ibrahim et al., 2024). Therefore, it can be concluded that the higher an employee's resilience, the higher their work ethic will be in the workplace. Based on the above considerations, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H3: Resilience has a positive and significant effect on work ethic

Resilience, Work Ethic, and Employee Performance

Resilience helps individuals remain resilient in the face of work pressure, change, and failure. Resilient employees are able to maintain motivation, manage emotions, and adapt quickly, thus remaining committed to their work (Luthans et al., 2006); Mazzetti et al., 2024). However, the effect of resilience on performance is not always direct. Several studies have shown that while resilience promotes positive attitudes, its impact on work outcomes often occurs through specific behavioral variables (Al Halbusi et al., 2022).

One of the variables that bridges this relationship is work ethic, namely the values and attitudes that encourage employees to work with discipline, diligence, responsibility, and integrity (Sinamo, 2011). Resilient employees tend to internalize

the values of work ethic more easily because they have high psychological resilience, optimism, and a long-term orientation toward work goals. In other words, resilience provides psychological energy, while work ethic directs that energy into productive work behavior.

Work ethic then acts as a behavioral mechanism that translates psychological resilience into measurable performance. Research shows that employees with a strong work ethic are more consistent in completing work on time, maintaining the quality of their work, and contributing more to the team (Khan et al., 2022). These results found that work ethic strengthens the influence of psychological factors on performance, both in the service sector and the oil and gas industry (Ilhami et al., 2024; Rahmawati et al., 2025). Thus, work ethic mediates the relationship between resilience and performance, as resilience fosters the formation of positive work values, which in turn leads to higher performance. Based on the above considerations, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H4: Work ethic mediates the effect of resilience on employee performance.

RESEARCH METHODS

The population in this study was all 466 employees of PT. Wanho Industries Indonesia. The sample size was 82 individuals using the Slovin formula. The sampling technique used was proportional sampling, where the number of samples from each group (stratum) in the population is taken proportionally according to the size of the subgroup within the population.

The data collection method used a questionnaire and literature review. The questionnaire was distributed to 82 employees of PT Wanho Industries Indonesia via Google Forms. The questionnaire used was a multiple-choice questionnaire, with each question item providing five answer choices, scored on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree) for all variables.

As a preliminary step before data collection, a validity and reliability test was conducted to determine the validity and reliability of the research instrument. The results of the validity test are shown in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Uji Validitas

No	Variabel	Indicator	r count	r Table	Information
1	Employee Performance (Y)	Y1	0,605	1,696	Valid
		Y2	0,752		Valid
		Y3	0,527		Valid
		Y4	0,279		Valid
		Y5	0,605		Valid
		Y6	0,752		Valid
		Y7	0,257		Valid
2	Resilience (X)	X1	0,721	1,696	Valid
		X2	0,696		Valid
		X3	0,358		Valid
		X4	0,573		Valid
3	Work Ethic (Z)	Z1	0,925	1,696	Valid
		Z2	0,464		Valid
		Z3	0,765		Valid
		Z4	0,855		Valid

Sumber: data primer yang diolah, tahun 2025

The results of the validity test show that the corrected item-total correlation value for each question is $> r\text{-table } 1.696$ with $df = 33 - 2 = 31$. The conclusion that can be drawn is that each question indicator used in this study is valid.

Table 3: Reliability Test Results

No	Variabel	Cronbach Alpha	Information
1.	Employee Performance	0.800	Reliabel
2.	Resilience	0.775	Reliabel
3.	Work Ethic	0.877	Reliabel

Sumber: data primer yang diolah, 2025

The results of the reliability test show that each variable has a Cronbach alpha based on standardized items > 0.70 , so it can be concluded that each construct is declared reliable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis of the relationships between variables can be explained diagrammatically in Figure 1 as follows:

Figure 1: Model of the Influence of Resilience on Employee Performance with Work Ethic as an Intervening Variable in the Operational Department of PT Wanho Indonesia

The results of the study show that the identity data of the 82 respondents is mostly female, namely 44 or 53.66%, while 38 or 46.34% are male. This is because the nature of work in the Operational Department, such as in the assembly or packaging section, requires precision and manual skills. In terms of age, most are between 21-30 years old, namely 30 people or 36.59 percent. This age range is a productive

workforce and easily adapts to technological changes. Respondents with high school education are 48 people or 58.54 percent, because in general employees are placed in positions that require more technical skills such as machine operators, production technicians. The length of service of respondents is between 1-2 years, namely 36 people or 43.90 percent, indicating the recruitment of new employees.

The results of the regression analysis indicate that the first proposed regression model is fit and suitable for use. This is indicated by the coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.756, which means that resilience and work ethic are able to explain 75.6% of the variation in employee performance, while the remainder is explained by other factors outside the model. The F test also shows a significance value of $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$, which indicates that the regression model is simultaneously significant.

The results of the classical assumption test show that the T-statistic KS is 0.120 with a significance of $0.200 > \alpha = 0.05$. This indicates that the residual distribution meets the assumption of normality, the VIF value is below 10 which indicates the absence of multicollinearity, and the heteroscedasticity test does not indicate that the significance value of resilience and work ethic is $< \alpha = 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the model is free from heteroscedasticity. Thus, the first structural model is declared fit and meets the requirements to test the influence between constructs in this study.

The first regression model hypothesis test shows that the coefficient value of the resilience variable (X) is positive at 0.167 with a significance of 0.121 ($> \alpha = 0.05$), meaning that the resilience variable has a positive but insignificant effect on employee performance. Therefore, the first hypothesis stating that resilience has a positive and significant effect is rejected. This means that employees in stressful or calm conditions have no effect on performance. The work ethic variable (Z) has a positive value of 0.772 with a significance of 0.000 ($< \alpha = 0.05$), meaning that work ethic has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Therefore, the second hypothesis stating that work ethic has a positive and significant effect on employee performance is accepted. This means that the better the work ethic, the more employee performance increases.

The results of the classical assumption test show that the T-statistic KS is 0.158 with a significance of $0.352 > \alpha = 0.05$. This indicates that the residual distribution meets the assumption of normality, and the heteroscedasticity test does not show that the resilience significance value is $< \alpha = 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the model is free from heteroscedasticity. Thus, the second structural model is declared fit and meets the requirements to test the influence between constructs in this study.

The second regression model hypothesis test showed a positive coefficient value of 0.508 for the resilience variable with a significance value of 0.003 ($< \alpha = 0.05$), indicating that the resilience variable has a positive and significant effect on work ethic. Therefore, the third hypothesis, which states that resilience has a positive and significant effect on work ethic, is accepted. This means that employees who are able to face difficulties will have an improved work ethic.

The intervening test shows that the indirect effect of resilience on employee performance through work ethic and the direct effect of resilience on work ethic obtained values of 0.639 and 0.508 with a significance of 0.003 ($\alpha < 0.05$). The value of the indirect effect is greater when compared to the direct effect between resilience on work ethic which can be written as follows: $0.639 > 0.508$. This means that work ethic can strengthen or mediate the effect of resilience on employee performance, so that work ethic can function as an intervening variable between the effect of resilience on employee performance. H4 which states that work ethic mediates the effect of resilience on employee performance is accepted.

The Effect of Resilience on Employee Performance

The results of this study indicate that resilience does not have a significant direct effect on employee performance. Although the relationship is positive (0.167), the significance value of 0.121 ($\alpha > 0.05$) indicates that employee psychological resilience is not sufficient to directly explain improvements in employee performance. This finding implies that an individual's ability to recover from stress, face challenges, and adapt to change does not automatically result in optimal performance if it is not balanced by other work behavioral factors.

In an organizational context, resilience plays a more significant role as an internal

psychological resource that helps individuals maintain emotional stability and motivation. Resilient employees are better able to cope with work pressures, but achieving performance in accordance with established standards in quality, quantity, and time requires more concrete behavioral mechanisms such as work ethic, commitment, discipline, and a sense of responsibility. This finding is inconsistent with research by Janitra et al., (2024) and Hardi et al., (2025), which found that resilience has a significant positive effect on employee performance.

The Influence of Work Ethic on Employee Performance

The findings indicate that work ethic has a positive and significant influence on employee performance, with a beta coefficient of 0.772 and a significance level of 0.000, $\alpha < 0.05$. These results confirm that work ethic is a primary factor determining the quality and level of performance achievement in an organization. A strong work ethic is reflected in discipline, hard work, honesty, diligence, and consistency in completing tasks. Employees with a strong work ethic are better able to manage time, maintain consistency in their work, and are more prepared to adapt to job demands, thus directly impacting improved performance. This finding aligns with behavioral work theory, which states that values, attitudes, and work motivation are key factors in achieving optimal performance. (Suryadi & Karyono, (2022) state that work ethic has a positive and significant influence on employee performance.

The Effect of Resilience on Work Ethic

The results of the study indicate that resilience has a positive and significant effect on work ethic, with a beta coefficient of 0.508 (sig 0.003). This indicates that an individual's ability to recover from stress, adapt to change, and maintain emotional stability directly contributes to the development of a strong work ethic. Resilient employees are better able to manage stress and maintain motivation despite facing various work obstacles.

This condition indicates that employees have a higher level of commitment, discipline, perseverance, and responsibility towards their work. Psychologically, resilience helps individuals view challenges as opportunities for growth, rather than obstacles. This is reflected in more stable and focused daily work behavior. Thus,

resilience serves as a crucial foundation that strengthens work attitudes and values that shape work ethic, as well as driving productive work behavior that contributes to organizational success.

Work Ethic Mediates the Effect of Resilience on Employee Performance.

The results of the study indicate that resilience directly influences work ethic, with a coefficient of 0.508 and a significance value of 0.003 (<0.05). This finding indicates that the higher an employee's resilience, the stronger their work ethic. Resilience reflects an individual's ability to recover from pressure, face challenges, and remain focused on goals, fostering positive work attitudes such as perseverance, commitment, and discipline. Thus, resilience has been shown to be an internal factor shaping the quality of an employee's work ethic.

The results of the mediation test show that resilience has an indirect effect on employee performance through work ethic, with a coefficient value of 0.639 and a significance level of 0.003 (<0.05). This indicates that work ethic plays a significant mediating role. As resilience increases, work ethic also improves, and this improvement in work ethic contributes to improved employee performance. In other words, resilience not only has a direct effect on performance but also produces additional impacts through strengthening work ethic.

This condition indicates that employee resilience will be more effective in improving performance when accompanied by a strong work ethic. Overall, these results confirm that work ethic is a crucial mechanism bridging the relationship between resilience and employee performance. This means that organizations need not only build individual resilience but also create a work environment that encourages the development of a strong work ethic so that employees can demonstrate optimal performance.

Conclusion

Resilience does not have a positive effect on employee performance. Therefore, resilience cannot be a direct predictor of performance. This indicates that psychological resilience is not sufficient to improve work performance without other

behavioral factors.

Work ethic has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Work ethic has been shown to be a key determinant in improving performance. Employees who are disciplined, committed, and possess high integrity tend to demonstrate better performance.

Resilience has a positive and significant impact on work ethic. Individual resilience has been shown to improve the quality of work ethic. Employees who possess adaptive skills and can cope with stress are more likely to maintain a positive and productive work attitude.

Work ethic mediates the effect of resilience on employee performance. Resilience does not directly influence performance, but exerts an indirect influence through work ethic. Thus, work ethic acts as an important mechanism bridging the relationship between resilience and performance, indicating pure mediation.

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